

CARDIAC REHABILITATION OF PATIENTS FOLLOWING MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION**Badan Maxim***medical student, Republic of Moldova***Abstract**

In 2017, mortality from cardiovascular diseases made up 58.4% of all deaths, of which ischemic heart disease (IHD) constituted 52.5% and 8.5% were due to acute myocardial infarction.

Cardiovascular rehabilitation is used to optimize the physical, psychological and social functioning of the patient who suffered a myocardial infarction. The session includes 3 phases: the warm-up, the actual training and the recovery (relaxation) phase. The program is individualized, so it is necessary to correctly select the type, intensity, duration and frequency for maximum therapeutic effect.

Exercise-based medical rehabilitation is a supplement to drug therapy and post-infarction interventional surgery, as it improves cardiopulmonary function, optimizes drug therapy, decreases risk factors, increases exercise tolerance, improves mental status, reduces the risk of repeated heart attack and cardiac mortality, and contributes to a successful return to work.

Keywords: Myocardial infarction, cardiovascular rehabilitation, physical exercises

Introduction

The incidence of myocardial infarction is continuously increasing. In 2015, mortality from cardiovascular diseases reached 17 million (31%) of the total of 54 million deaths worldwide, of which the share of coronary diseases constituted 48%.

Annually cardiovascular diseases cause 3.9 million (45%) deaths in Europe and over 1.8 million (37%) deaths in the European Union (EU). The global cost of CVD for the EU economy was estimated at 210 billion euro per year. [2]

The mortality of patients with STEMI is influenced by multiple factors, among them advanced age, Killip class, delay in treatment, the existence of STEMI networks based on the emergency medical system, therapeutic strategy, the presence of antecedents of myocardial infarction, diabetes, renal insufficiency, the number of coronary arteries the ejection fraction of the left ventricle is also affected.[3] Although the incidence of myocardial infarction is low in industrialized countries, partly due to improved health systems and the implementation of effective public health strategies, it is increasing in developing countries such as South Asia, parts of Latin America, and Eastern Europe. [4]

The term "cardiac rehabilitation" refers to coordinated interventions aimed at optimizing the physical, psychological and social functioning of the cardiac patient, in addition to stabilizing, slowing or even reversing the progression of the underlying atherosclerotic processes, thereby reducing morbidity and mortality.

The program involves education, exercise, risk factor modification, and counseling. It is targeted by specialized medical personnel and adapted to each individual.

The recovery of patients with cardiovascular diseases has positive results because it improves exercise tolerance, thus leading to a decrease in mortality.

A meta-analysis based on a review of 48 randomized trials comparing the outcomes of exercise-based rehabilitation with usual care showed a 20% reduction in total mortality and a 26% reduction in the cardiac death rate with exercise-based rehabilitation physical. [5]

As a consequence, healthcare professionals have designed cardiac rehabilitation (CR) programs for patients with MI. RC generally consists of three phases:

I - acute phase of CR after an acute event (1-14 days)

II - Second phase of cardiac rehabilitation (1-6 months)

III - The third (maintenance) phase of cardiac rehabilitation (6-12 months) [6]

RC aims at physical recovery, improvement of quality of life, psycho-social health and a decrease in the recurrence of hospitalization and death.

Aim of the study:

Studying the influence of therapeutic physical exercise complexes used in the rehabilitation of patients with myocardial infarction to assess the beneficial effects on health.

Results:

Literature data suggest the importance of medical rehabilitation treatment for post-infarction patients in combination with pharmacological treatment. The session includes 3 phases: the warm-up, the actual training and the recovery (relaxation) phase. The program is individualized, so it is necessary to correctly select the type, intensity, duration and frequency for maximum therapeutic effect, periodically 3 to 5 sessions per week, with the recommended duration from 20 to 60 minutes. The criterion to dose physical effort is frequency of cardiac contractions. [7]

The warm-up period, which aims to increase myocardial blood supply, increase the flexibility of soft tissues, joint mobilization.

The actual, supervised training is considered optimal with a duration of 20-30 minutes; it has been shown by numerous studies that the best results are obtained through anaerobic exercises that include repetitive movements and engage large muscle groups. [8]

The recovery period consists of performing low-intensity exercises and stretching; gradual recovery prevents the appearance of rhythm disturbances.

The beneficial effects are:

1) Anti-atherosclerotic, due to improving the lipid profile, increasing insulin sensitivity.

2) Anti-ischemic -decreasing myocardial O₂ demand, increasing coronary flow.

3) Antithrombotic - decrease in platelet aggregation, increase in fibrinolysis, decrease in fibrinogen, decrease in blood viscosity.

4) Antiarrhythmic-increasing vagal tone, decreasing adrenergic activity. [9][10]

Conclusions:

Exercise-based medical rehabilitation is a supplement to drug therapy and post-infarction interventional surgery, as it improves cardiopulmonary function, optimizes drug therapy, decreases risk factors, increases exercise tolerance, improves mental status, hemodynamic and metabolic function, reduces the risk of reinfarction and cardiac mortality. As part of a cardiac rehabilitation program, physical activity helps reduce psychological maladjustment and contributes to a successful return to work.

References

- 1 Fourth universal definition of myocardial infarction (2018) *European Heart Journal*, Volume 40, Issue 3, 14 January 2019, Pages 237–269, <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehy462>
- 2 WILKINS, E., et al. *European Cardiovascular Disease Statistics 2017*. In: *European Heart Network*. Brussels. 2017. 192 pagini. www.ehnheart.org
- 3 2015 ESC Guidelines for the management of acute coronary syndromes in patients presenting without persistent ST-segment elevation: Task Force for the Management of Acute Coronary Syndromes in Patients Presenting without Persistent ST-Segment Elevation of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC). *European Heart Journal*, Volume 37, Issue 3, 14 January 2016, Pages 267–315, <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehv320>
- 4 Chadwick Jayaraj, J., Davatyan, K., Subramanian, S. S., & Priya, J. (2019). Epidemiology of Myocardial Infarction. *Myocardial Infarction*. doi:10.5772/intechopen.74768
- 5 Leon, A. S. (2005). Cardiac Rehabilitation and Secondary Prevention of Coronary Heart Disease: An American Heart Association Scientific Statement From the Council on Clinical Cardiology (Subcommittee on Exercise, Cardiac Rehabilitation, and Prevention) and the Council on Nutrition, Physical Activity, and Metabolism (Subcommittee on Physical Activity), in Collaboration With the American Association of Cardiovascular and Pulmonary Rehabilitation. *Circulation*, 111(3), 369–376. doi:10.1161/01.cir.0000151788.08740.5c
- 6 Piepoli, M. F., Corrà, U., Benzer, W., Bjarnason-Wehrens, B., Dendale, P., Gaita, D., ... Schmid, J.-P. (2010). Secondary prevention through cardiac rehabilitation: from knowledge to implementation. A position paper from the Cardiac Rehabilitation Section of the European Association of Cardiovascular Prevention and Rehabilitation. *European Journal of Cardiovascular Prevention & Rehabilitation*, 17(1), 1–17. doi:10.1097/hjr.0b013e3283313592
- 7 Dr Arthur S. Leon (2000). Exercise Following Myocardial Infarction. , 29(5), 301–311. doi:10.2165/00007256-200029050-00002
- 8 Pollock, M. L., Gaesser, G. A., Butcher, J. D., Despres, J.-P., Dishman, R. K., Franklin, B. A., & Garber, C. E. (1998). ACSM Position Stand: The Recommended Quantity and Quality of Exercise for Developing and Maintaining Cardiorespiratory and Muscular Fitness, and Flexibility in Healthy Adults. *Medicine & Science in Sports & Exercise*, 30(6), 975–991. doi:10.1097/00005768-199806000-00032
- 9 Ekblom, Orjan; Ek, Amanda; Cider, Åsa; Hambraeus, Kristina; Börjesson, Mats (2018). Increased Physical Activity Post-Myocardial Infarction Is Related to Reduced Mortality: Results From the SWEDEHEART Registry. *Journal of the American Heart Association*, 7(24), – . doi:10.1161/JAHA.118.010108
- 10 Xing, Ying; Yang, Si-Dong; Wang, Man-Man; Feng, Ya-Shuo; Dong, Fang; Zhang, Feng (2020). The Beneficial Role of Exercise Training for Myocardial Infarction Treatment in Elderly. *Frontiers in Physiology*, 11(), 270– . doi:10.3389/fphys.2020.00270